

Activity Measurement with Resin-Membrane Electrode (Part. I)*

A. Sarkar, S. C. Ghosh and S. K. Mukherjee

Validity of cation-selective membrane in determining H⁺-ion activity has been tested. H⁺-ion activity in simple and polyelectrolyte has been determined by using the membrane electrode.

The applicability of the membrane electrode in the simple acid-base titration as well as poly acid = simple base titration has also been examined. An attempt has been made to determine the Na⁺ ion bound by polyanion chain during the neutralisation of poly acid by NaOH.

The electrolyte solutions, separated by a permeable or semi-permeable membrane differ in their electric potential. This difference in potential is called membrane potential which can be measured by inserting suitable electrodes into the solutions.

The membrane potential E_M , observed between two ionic solutions separated by a membrane follows Nernst equation within a certain range of concentration¹. The membrane potential composed of three different potentials, two being opposed Donnan potential at the membrane surfaces and the third is the diffusion potential across the membrane phase. The diffusion potential term vanishes, provided the membrane excludes co-ions owing to high concentration of fixed charge in the membrane phase and E_M takes the form of Nernst equation, i.e.,

$$E_M = \frac{RT}{zF} \ln \frac{(a_+)_I}{(a_+)_{II}} \quad \dots (1)$$

where $(a_+)_I$ and $(a_+)_{II}$ are the cation activities at the two sides of the membrane.

At higher concentrations, the measured E_M deviates from the Nernst equation due to failure of the membrane to exclude co-ions leading to change in Donnan potentials and to establishment of a diffusion potential across the membrane phase. The maximum value of E_M is often realisable with the help of charged membrane of low porosity but within a limited range of concentrations.

At all stages, however, the membrane potential is found to depend on the concentration and nature of the electrolyte, their ratios on the two sides of the membrane as well as on the nature of the membranes themselves. The membrane potential, E_M given by the equation (1) is the maximum value obtainable with an ideally selective membrane. Although selective membranes are not realisable in practice, membranes are almost 100 per cent selective within a certain concentration range, which means that factors contributing to the non-ideality cancel each other in the particular concentration range or become negligible.

The investigation described in the present paper is a part of work on the ion-activity measurements by using resin membrane electrode. The validity of the resin membrane

* Presented at the 6th Annual Convention of Indian Chemical Society.

1. F. Helfferich, 'Ion Exchange', McGraw-Hill Book Company, 1962, p. 371.

electrode used in determining hydrogen-ion activity in the simple and poly-electrolyte solutions was critically examined. The applicability of the membrane electrode in acid-base titration was also verified.

EXPERIMENTAL

Polyacrylic acid (PAA) was prepared by the usual procedure i.e., by polymerising acrylic acid with Benzoyl peroxide as initiator. The solution of the poly acid was dialysed against de-ionised water to remove low molecular weight species and impurities. All simple acids and bases used in the work were analytical grade chemicals. De-ionised water was used throughout.

Membrane MC-3470XL used was supplied by Dr. C. Calmon of Ionac Chemical Company, Birmingham, N.J. It is a heterogeneous, strongly ionised permselective type ion exchange membrane. The membranes were cut into pieces and attached to the ends of pyrex tubing with polystyrene based adhesive. The membrane surfaces were kept for 24 hrs. in contact with the same concentration of the ions, the activity of which was intended to measure. The E.M.F. measurements were done by using two tiny saturated calomel electrodes placed on the two sides of the membrane. The potentials were measured with the help of a potentiometer and a sensitive galvanometer. Any pair of electrodes showing an asymmetry potential greater than 0.1 mv was rejected. The solutions were replaced by fresh one before measurement of E.M.F.

RESULTS

The predicted values of E.M.F. with known H^+ ion activities on the two sides of the membrane agree quite well as is evidenced from Table I.

TABLE I

Inner Soln. $a_{H^+} \times 10^3$	Outer Soln. $a_{H^+} \times 10^3$	Theoretical EMF(mv) at 25°	Observed EMF(mv) at 25°
9.048	4.6425	17.11	17.10
4.6425	0.9656	40.13	40.10
0.9656	0.4873	17.53	17.50

TABLE II

Inner Soln. $a_{H^+} \times 10^3$	Outer PAA Soln. gms/litre	EMF (mv) at 30°	$a_{H^+} \times 10^4$	$\frac{a_{H^+}}{C} \times 10^4$
0.9656	6.7008	-16.0	17.84	2.669
"	6.2820	-15.0	17.17	2.733
"	5.8850	-10.5	14.45	2.463
"	4.8860	-10.6	14.50	2.968
"	4.1880	-7.3	12.77	2.423
4.6425	3.490	34.6	12.30	3.525
0.9656	2.792	-1.0	10.03	3.586
4.6425	1.396	52.5	6.19	4.434
0.9656	0.5584	32.2	2.806	5.025

In calculation the theoretical EMF the standard values² of the activity co-efficients of HCl are used.

Fig. 1 shows the variation of a_{H^+} of polyacrylic acid with concentration and Table II, gives the respective EMF values. The increase of $\frac{a_{H^+}}{C}$ with dilution explains the weak electrolytic nature of polyacrylic acid. Ionisation is facilitated with dilution.

The nature of neutralisation curve of HCl with NaOH by means of membrane electrode has been shown in Fig. II. The end point obtained by this technique agrees well with the value found from titration using indicator.

Table III shows the mobility ratio U_{H^+}/U_{Na^+} calculated using the general equation

$$E_M = \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{a_A^I}{a_A^{II} + a_B^{II}} \cdot \frac{U_D}{U_A} \quad (2)$$

A and D are monovalent cations, U_A and U_D being their respective mobilities³.

2. H. S. Harned and Owen, 'The Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Soln.', Reinhold Publishing Corporation, 1950.
3. S. K. Mukherjee, Bulletin of the National Institute of Sciences of India, 1961, No. 29, 214.

Fig. III shows the result of the neutralisation of PAA with NaOH, *pH*-metrically and by the membrane electrode. The end point obtained by these two different methods as well as by titration using phenolphthalein agrees well.

Various experimental results⁴⁻⁷ on the activity of counter ions have shown that a large fraction of them are associated with polyions, and ion-pair, site-binding type models have been proposed to explain them. Table IV shows the amount of Na⁺ bound by the polyelectrolyte chain, calculated from equation (2). The mobility ratio used in the calculation has been shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Inner Soln. a_{Na^+}	Outer Soln. a_{H^+}	EMF (mv) 30°	$\frac{U_{H^+}}{U_{Na^+}}$
0.00292 +	0.0009656 -	-4.0	3.534
0.00877 -	0.0009656 +	17.6	4.669
0.00292 +	0.0046425 -	49.3	4.410

The average value of $\frac{U_{H^+}}{U_{Na^+}}$, 4 is taken for calculation.

It is evident that the amount of cations bound depends upon the degree of neutralisation.

The phenomenon may be explained by assuming the effect of shape change on binding of ions by polyelectrolyte chain. It has been found from viscosity change that the PAA molecule unfolds itself with neutralisation. The change of shape of the macromolecule may be correlated with its binding capacity of cations. At the very beginning the polyelectrolyte molecule is in the coiled state with a few ionised H⁺ ions near its surface. With the addition

4. W. Kern, *Makromol. Chem.*, 1948, **2**, 279.
5. J. Huizenga, P. F. Griegen and F. T. Wall, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 2638.
6. F. Oosawa, N. Imai and I. Karawa, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1954, **13**, 93.
7. U. P. Struss and P. D. Ross, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 5292, 5295.

of NaOH these H^+ ions are neutralised and the equivalent number of Na^+ ions are formed, most of which are free. But the more the PAA is neutralised the greater is the expansion of the polyelectrolyte chain due to the breaking of intramolecular hydrogen bonds. At this stage the total amount of Na^+ ions formed is not free; a fraction of it is held bound by the charged polymer chain. Charging of the polymer chain and its binding capacity increase simultaneously. The results reported by other authors are of similar nature⁸⁻¹⁰

TABLE IV

Inner Soln., $a_{Na^+} = 0.00292$			P.A.A. Conc. = 0.8%			
Added $a_{Na^+} \times 10^3$	Percentage of neutralisation	pH	EMF (mv) 30°	Free $a_{Na^+} \times 10^3$	Bound $a_{Na^+} \times 10^3$	Percentage of Na^+ ion free
0	...	3.92	36.0
0.0836	2.534	4.21	39.0
0.1680	5.093	4.21	42.0
0.8401	25.48	5.35	39.6	0.6048	0.2353	71.96
1.680	50.93	6.15	33.4	0.7905	0.8894	47.06
2.520	76.40	6.59	30.4	0.8907	1.6294	35.35
3.024	91.68	6.88	25.0	1.1004	1.9235	36.38
3.193	96.81	6.95	24.0	1.1440	2.0484	35.83
3.298	100.00	7.02	24.0	1.1446	2.1534	33.79
3.359		7.10	28.6			
3.444		7.15	27.8			
3.528		7.15	23.9			
3.696		7.28	23.0			
4.200		7.31	18.0			
4.368		7.42	20.6			
4.536		7.54	20.0			
4.704		7.50	17.4			
4.872		7.56	15.3			

It should be pointed out that underlying the discussions made above is the arbitrary assumption of the idea of a single ion activity. This approach has, however, been questioned by a number of authors¹¹.

Sincere thanks are due to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research for granting financial assistance to one of the authors (A.S.).

Department of Agriculture,
University of Calcutta,
35, Ballygunge Circular Road,
Calcutta 19.

Received June 7, 1969

8. Z. Alexandrowicz, *J. Polymer. Sci.*, 1960, **43**, 337.
9. J. A. Marinsky and A. Chatterjee, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, **67**, 47.
10. A. Sarkar, 'Studies in Solution and Nuclear Chemistry', 1965, AEC, Contract No. A (30), 2269.
11. K. S. Spiegler and M. R. J. Wyllie, "Physical Techniques in Biological Research", G. Oster and A. W. Pollister (eds.), Vol. 2, p. 301, Academic Press, Inc., New York, 1956.